

ASSESSMENT OF THYROID ENLARGEMENT IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

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Abstract. In this research study, the authors determined and evaluated the dimensions of the thyroid gland in patients with bronchial asthma. As a result of the research, it was found that among the autoimmune diseases of the thyroid gland, autoimmune thyroiditis is more common in patients with bronchial asthma, among them, the female gender prevails, and thyroid gland enlargement of the 1st degree is more common.

Key words: bronchial asthma, autoimmune thyroiditis, thyroid gland, autoimmune diseases of the thyroid gland, thyroid gland enlargement.

The urgency of the problem. The etiology of bronchial asthma (BA) is diverse, and it is also relevant due to its prevalence in the world, frequent occurrence of severe complications despite the availability of modern methods of treatment, and high risk of death [1,2,3]. Autoimmune diseases of the thyroid gland are one of the main trigger factors in the development of bronchial asthma, and the combination of these two pathologies seriously harms the patient's health [4,5,6].

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the enlargement of the thyroid gland in patients with bronchial asthma.

Research materials and methods. During the study, 287 patients with bronchial asthma were studied. Among them, 250 patients with bronchial asthma and autoimmune thyroiditis, 37 patients with BA and toxic goiter were involved. Among patients with BA and autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT), 159 were women and 91 were men. The average age of women was 51.4 ± 2.01 years, and

that of men was 48.76 ± 2.01 years. 19 patients with toxic goiter were women (mean age 46.3 ± 2.01) and 18 were men (mean age 50.8 ± 2.01).

Results of the study. In patients with BA and AIT, 38 patients had grade 0 thyroid enlargement, 165 patients had grade 1 enlargement, and 47 patients had grade 2 thyroid enlargement. Among patients with BA and toxic goiter, only 1st and 2nd degree enlargement was observed, of which 14 patients with 1st degree enlargement and 23 patients with 2nd degree enlargement were observed. Normal thyroid sizes were not observed among those with goiter. Patients with euthyroidism (27.2%) with thyroid gland enlargement of the 0th degree were the majority compared to patients in the other groups, and among the patients with the enlargement of the 1st degree, the patients with subclinical hypothyroidism were the majority (76.9%, $r \geq 0.05$). . Manifest (65.3%, $r \geq 0.05$) and subclinical thyrotoxicosis (66.6%, $r \geq 0.05$) cases were noted among patients with thyroid gland enlargement of the 2nd degree. No grade 0 enlargement was observed among patients with BA and toxic goiter. Grade 1 and 2 enlargement did not show a reliable difference in patients with mild (41%; 59%, respectively) and moderate thyrotoxicosis (35%, 65%, respectively).

Summary. Among the autoimmune diseases of the thyroid gland in patients with bronchial asthma, autoimmune thyroiditis is more common, and among them, representatives of the female sex predominate. Grade 1 thyroid enlargement was more common among patients with AIT. Grade 0 goiter was not observed among those with toxic goiter.

References:

1. Мальцева Т.А. Особенности функционального состояния тиреоидного статуса у больных с бронхиальной астмы. // Киберленинка. 2010. № 4 (64). С. 89-92.
2. Попова Н.В., Куделя Л.М, Бондарь И.А. Клинические особенности течения бронхиальной астмы в сочетании с компенсированным гипотиреозом у больных пожилого возраста // Профилактическая и клиническая медицина. 2010. № 3. С. 253-257.
3. Попова Н.В., Куделя Л.М, Бондарь И.А. Клинические особенности течения бронхиальной астмы у больных в сочетании с гипотиреозом // Сибирское медицинское обозрение. 2010. № 4 (64). С. 89-92.
4. Dama M, Steiner M, Lieshout RV.J. Thyroid peroxidase autoantibodies and perinatal depression risk: A systematic review. *Affect Disord.* 2016 Jul 1;198:108-21. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2016.03.021.
5. Choi HG, Kim TJ, Hong SK, Min C, Yoo DM, Kim H, Lee JS. Thyroid Diseases and Chronic Rhinosinusitis: A Nested Case-Control Study Using a National Health

Screening Cohort. Int J Environ Res Public Health. 2022 Jul 8;19(14):8372. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19148372.

6. Cardet JC, Bulkhi AA, Lockey RF.J. Nonrespiratory Comorbidities in Asthma. Allergy Clin Immunol Pract. 2021 Nov;9(11):3887-3897. doi: 10.1016/j.jaip.2021.08.027.

